

BIM TOOLS IN ORGANIZATIONAL AND TECHNOLOGICAL SOLUTIONS FOR MONOLITHIC-FRAME CONSTRUCTION

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With the growing demand for digitization in the construction industry, BIM and IT technologies have become integral to construction processes. In traditional design workflows, labor costs are typically distributed as follows: 30% for developing engineering solutions, 10% for coordination and approval, and 60% for preparing and issuing design documentation.

BIM technologies significantly change this distribution compared to traditional methods. BIM enables higher-quality design solutions, improves construction productivity, and fosters more effective collaboration throughout the entire building life cycle. It also provides a deeper understanding of structural systems, supporting the validation and approval of design decisions. By optimizing both the design and construction of monolithic frame buildings, BIM tools offer the following advantages:

RFI (Requests for Information). Improved transparency in project management processes such as submitting and responding to requests for information.

Submittals. Efficient management of project information through flexible workflows for creating and tracking digital records.

Elimination of redundant documentation. Prevents the creation of outdated, incomplete, or inaccurate drawings, models, and documents that otherwise lead to additional approvals, delays, and information requests.

Coordination and collaboration among multidisciplinary teams. Enhances communication between disciplines, reduces conflicts, and ensures that projects are delivered on schedule while saving financial resources.

Paperless safety management. Digital safety management systems extend across the entire project lifecycle, helping to attract investment, win more contracts, and improve project outcomes.

Quality management. The costliest quality issues in construction are those that go undetected; BIM enables early identification and prevention.

Constructability review. Identifies design errors, omissions, and inaccuracies that could cause rework in the field, thereby reducing costs and schedule overruns.

Design collaboration. By unifying design teams, BIM accelerates project execution, minimizes rework, and enables safe real-time co-editing while simplifying project data exchange.

Construction data and analytics. A typical project may generate thousands of open issues, hundreds of RFIs, and numerous change requests; BIM provides a structured environment for managing and analyzing this data.

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